

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

UTILIZATION OF TRAINING RECIPES AND SUBSTANCES USED FOR DEGASSING MILITARY EQUIPMENT OBJECTS

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ABSTRACT

Anthropogenic pollution caused by the human activity is a constant source of negative impact on the environment. The conduct of local military operations leads to the fact that military exercises are held in various countries and training recipes with different action functions are used to simulate the effects of toxic substances on living organisms and military equipment. The article provides data on the disposal of educational formulations RD-2 and RD-A, IV-B, IV-2 and dichloramines (dichloramine B, dichloramine T and dichloramine CB). Due to their properties, dichloramines are in demand not only for decontamination of military equipment, but also in the military industry, aviation, and for eliminating the consequences of contamination of the environment and equipment with spilled leaded petroleum products. Degassing products from dichloramines decompose to release hydrogen chloride, which causes corrosion of metal surfaces. As a result, after treating military equipment with dichloramine solutions, it is recommended to clean and lubricate metal parts.

Keywords: toxic substances, simulators, disinfection, training formulations I V-B and I V-2, RD-2 and RD-A.

In continuation of previously published works on the disposal of toxic substances [1,2], the authors in this publication present research on the disinfection of some military recipes. To train military personnel in practical skills of conducting combat operations in conditions of the use of toxic substances, special training recipes are being developed that simulate contamination of the environment, including military equipment.

Military training recipes are a mixture of substances that have a strong irritating effect on the body.

The irritating substances themselves - irritants - have various effects (tear lacrimals, sneezing agents - sternites, pain algogens) and are used to suppress and eliminate mass disorders that pose a public danger.

The main condition for educational recipes is their versatility and safety of use [3-7]. Currently, some military facilities have accumulated a significant amount of unused stocks of simulant recipes, the production of which has been suspended due to their high toxicity. These simulators include the IV-B and IV-2 formulations, which are a mixture of neutral substances with

substances that have a strong irritating effect on a living organism, simulating the effects of a highly toxic substance – “Iprit”. Both training recipes are delivered to the troops in thick-walled iron barrels L-100, L-150, L-200, L-250 and have an unpleasant odor. The term of storage of the recipes has expired, which led to the gradual depressurization of the containers and the dilapidation of the premises in which they are stored.

IV-B recipe

The training recipe IV-B is a viscous oily liquid of brownish-brown color with a freezing point of minus 45°C. The recipe is non-flammable. Contamination of the terrain and military equipment with the recipe is carried out using imitation grenades and land mines (IGS and IF) [7].

IV-B is prepared on the basis of crystalline chloroacetophenone or its mother solution in carbon tetrachloride mixed with petroleum bitumen, chloropicrin and turpentine.

Training recipe IV-2 is a viscous liquid of dark brown color with a freezing point of minus 40°C. A recipe is also prepared on the basis of crystalline chloroacetophenone in green oil mixed with chloropicrin and

turpentine. Contamination with the recipe is carried out using auto-filling stations or improvised means (brush), since the recipe is flammable.

Table 1.

Composition of the IV-B training recipe.

Components	Number of components per 1000 kg of recipe	
	On crystalline chloroacetophenone	On mother liquor chloroacetophenone
Chloroacetophenone	50	---
Sulfate turpentine	65	65
Chloracetophenone stock solution	—	108
Chloropicrin technical	40	40
Carbon tetrachloride	795	737
Petroleum bitumen	50	50

Table 2.

Composition of the training recipe IV-2.

Components	Number of components per 1000 kg of recipe	
	On crystalline chloroacetophenone	On mother liquor chloroacetophenone
Chloroacetophenone	78	---
Sulfate turpentine	105	105
Chloracetophenone stock solution	—	169
Chloropicrin technical	67	67
Green oil	750	659

As can be seen from the tables, the main components of both formulations (chloropicrin, chloroacetophenone), which cause irritation and imitate the effect of "Iprit", are the same.

The effect of chloroacetophenone and chloropicrin is well known. These are lacrimants that cause irritation of the mucous membrane and tearing.

The third component, designed to enhance the toxicity of the formulations, is sulfate turpentine, which not only acts as a solvent, but also gives the formulation an unpleasant garlic odor.

Carbon tetrachloride is a non-flammable solvent.

Petroleum bitumen imitates the appearance of persistent toxic substances and imparts the necessary viscosity.

Green oil, a solvent that imparts stability to the formulation, is a mixture of high molecular weight aromatic hydrocarbons.

RECIPLES RD-A and RD-2

Along with recipes that simulate the contamination of military equipment and the surrounding area with toxic substances, there are also military training recipes that serve to decontaminate these toxic compounds.

For example, degassing removes toxic substances (TS) from the surface of contaminated objects, military equipment and weapons, personal protective equipment for skin and terrain [8-10]. Degassing reagents, reacting with toxic substances, transform them into non-toxic compounds. A distinction is made between degassing occurring naturally due to the evaporation and absorption of TS and artificially - by treating individual areas of the surface with which people come into contact.

There are also mechanical, physical and physicochemical degassing of surfaces. During mechanical and physicochemical degassing, the TS is removed from the

surface by weathering and washing off with water, but the TS itself is not destroyed. During chemical decontamination, the contaminated surface reacts with the degassing formulation to form slightly toxic and non-toxic products.

In such cases, aqueous solutions of alkalis, hypochlorites and various chloramines are used [11]. Along with substances with oxidative-chlorinating action, alkaline degassing reagents (caustic alkalis, soda, ammonia) are also used. The main components included in the formulations are alkali metal alcoholates, surfactants, and protic and aprotic solvents. Degassing substances also include water, which decomposes TS when boiled, so it is used for degassing clothing and some personal protective equipment [12-15].

When degassing weapons, military equipment, exposed areas of human skin, equipment, uniforms, polydegassing formulations RD-2 and RD-A are used, the disposal of which is the subject of our research.

Degassing formulation RD-2 is a mobile liquid from light yellow to brown in color, and is intended for degassing weapons and military equipment, personal protective equipment for skin and terrain contaminated with such poisonous gases as VX, "Soman" and "Iprit". For effective degassing with the RD-2 formulation, the contaminated surfaces of objects must be dry. Having a wide temperature range for use from + 40°C to - 60°C, with a flash point of + 31°C, RD-2 is the main formulation for use in winter conditions.

The consumption rate of the formulation for mustard gas contamination is 0.4 l/m², and for degassing the area is 1.5-2 l/m².

The RD-2 recipe is supplied to the troops in finished form in hermetically sealed steel barrels. Flammable. The ingress of water and prolonged contact with

the atmosphere lead to a decrease in the degassing ability of the formulation. In a hermetically sealed container, the properties of RD-2 are preserved for 5 years, and in case of depressurization - for a week.

Recycling of the recipe leads to the further use of final products with new consumer qualities.

Degassing formulation RD-A is intended for partial degassing of small arms, armored vehicles and equipment at temperatures from +40°C to -37°C with a consumption rate of 0.4 l/m².

Table 3.

Composition of RD-2 and RD-A

RD - 2	RD - A
Chlorobenzene	Gasoline B - 70
Kerosene	n-Butyl alcohol
Isobutyl alcohol	Ethylenediamine
Ethyl cellosolve	Ethyl cellosolve
Oxyphos	Sodium hydroxide

DICHLORAMINES

Chlorine-containing compounds-chloramines are also used to degas weapons and military equipment. Due to their properties, dichloramines are in demand in the military industry, aviation, and for eliminating the consequences of contamination of the environment and equipment with spilled ethylated petroleum products.

There are: dichloramine B, dichloramine T and dichloramine CB. Dichloramine. B and T are close in properties.

Dichloramine T (toluenesulfamide) is a yellowish crystalline substance with a melting point of 83 ° C, insoluble in water and capable of explosive decomposition under mechanical stress. Flash point is 196-200°C. Decomposes with concentrated acids and alkalis. Dichloramines are also an effective means for neutralizing mustard gas. A 10% solution of dichloramine in dichloroethane (degassing solution No. 1) has a chlorinating effect on Mustard gas and converts it into sulfonic acid (O=S-CH₂-CH₂Cl), which is a valuable reagent in the production of chemical and biologically active substances (active content chlorine not less than 52%). Sulfonic acid is also used in the production of inhibitors and in the cleaning of paraffin and asphalt-resin deposits in oil pipelines. The resulting sulfonic acids do not have toxic properties. Degassing solution No. 1 also effectively neutralizes such toxic substances as lewisite, trichlorethylamine in summer conditions, and in winter conditions, due to the freezing temperature (-35 ° C), only Mustard gas. Due to instability during long-term storage, degassing solution No. 1 should be prepared shortly before use. Toluenesulfamide is a shine-forming additive, which at the same time promotes the formation of non-brittle elastic nickel coatings.

Toluenesulfamides are intermediate products for the production of polymer materials, reagents in or-

ganic synthesis, as plasticizers for cellulose ethers. Toluenesulfamide is the starting material for the production of paraactivin, a bleaching agent used in the textile industry.

Dichloramine B (dichlorobenzenesulfamide) is a crystalline substance of a dirty yellow color, a flammable substance - it burns with a smoky flame when in contact with fire (especially oils, paints), and has an irritating effect on the skin and respiratory tract. Dichloramine B in carbon tetrachloride is used for decontamination of aircraft. Dichloramine. B is packaged in plywood-stamped barrels in polyethylene bags with a capacity of 50 liters. The substance decomposes in light with loss of active chlorine: decomposition is accelerated by traces of iron when heated. It is insoluble in water, and upon prolonged boiling with water it slowly decomposes. It dissolves in sodium hydroxide solution to form monochloramine B. The decomposition of dichloramine B is carried out by hydrolysis in an acidic environment and upon heating with the formation of monochloramine B.

EXPERIMENTAL PART

Disposal of IV-B and IV-2

The conversion of toxic substances from military training formulations IV-B and IV-2 into non-toxic ones is carried out through the destruction reaction of chloropicrin and chloroacetophenone until complete decomposition. In case of IV-B, carbon tetrachloride has been initially removed from the formulation by distillation, the bottom residue has been treated with an alkaline alcohol solution to obtain crystalline low-toxic organic compounds and inorganic salts - sodium chloride and carbonate.

The destruction reaction proceeds according to the following scheme:

chloroacetophenone

Chloropicrin

Carbon tetrachloride is distilled off from a sample of the IV-B recipe (100 g) at a temperature of 76-78°C.

Separately, methyl or ethyl alcohol is placed in a three-neck flask with a stirrer with a reflux condenser and a

thermometer, and sodium hydroxide is added while stirring (in a weight ratio of alcohol: alkali - 10:1) until completely dissolved. Preference has been given to the use of methyl alcohol, since it produces a more concentrated alkali solution, which leads to a decrease in the duration of the decomposition reaction. The temperature increases to 60°C and with constant stirring, the still residue is fed in portions. As the decomposition reaction progresses (after about 1.5 hours), a sample is taken from the reaction mixture and a TLC test is carried out for the presence of in the starting chloropicrin and chloroacetophenone (eluent hexane: chloroform: methanol = 7: 2: 1). 2.5 – 3 hours the reaction is completed, as evidenced by the absence of traces of the starting compounds on TLC plates. Next, methanol is

distilled off (the latter can be reused for these purposes). The remaining solid oil is non-toxic, non-irritant and can be disposed of.

A sample of IV-2 is added in portions to a methyl alkali solution prepared in advance. Next, the reaction is carried out according to the above-described decomposition reaction of the IV-B formulation.

Utilization of RD-2 and RD-A

Since the compounds included in the formulations of degassing substances RD-2 and RD-A are known, the goal of our work is to develop methods for their extraction and reuse in industry (recycling). For recycling, they were distilled at atmospheric pressure and in vacuum (10 mmHg) in the temperature range of 88-250°C, selecting each fraction separately.

Table 1.

Physicochemical constants of RD-2 and RD-A			
Components	n_D^{20}	d_4^{20}	$t_{\text{kin}}^{\circ}\text{C}$
RD-2			
chlorobenzene	1.5248	1.1066	132
kerosene			150-250
potassium isobutoxide mixed with isobutanol	1.3977	0,8027	108
ethyl cellosolve	-	-	135.6
oxyphos			
RD-A			
gasoline B-70			88
n.butyl alcohol	1.3993	0,8095	117.7
ethylenediamine	1.4508	0,8977	116.5
ethyl cellosolve	-	-	135.6

Utilization of dichloramines

The utilization of the provided dichloramine B is carried out as follows. Dichloramine is added to an aqueous solution of sodium hydroxide at a temperature of 45-50°C without stirring and kept for 2 hours at this temperature. Next, the reaction mixture is decanted for

The isolated monochloramine B is a strong oxidizing and chlorinating agent. Further, by hydrolysis, monochloramine B gradually decomposes into benzenesulfamide and sodium hypochlorite (an unstable compound) (decomposition is noticeably accelerated

The utilization of dichloramine T is also carried out in an aqueous alkali solution, heating to 60°C without stirring: load dichloramine T into an aqueous alkali

Similar to dichloramine B, dichloramine T easily hydrolyzes when heated with water, forming p-toluenesulfamide:

A qualitative color reaction to benzene sulfonamide is the formation of dark crystals when mixed with

about a day, the isolated crystals are washed several times, and after recrystallization in a chloroform solution, yellow crystals with a melting point of 66°C are obtained. The resulting monochloramine B can be used as a chemical reagent in fine organic synthesis.

by heating), and its antiseptic effect is based on this property of monochloramine B.

Sodium hypochlorite is a strong oxidizing agent. It is used as a disinfectant in medicine.

solution, leave for 5 hours, leave for 24 hour. In this case, white crystals of the sodium salt of toluenesulfamide fall out:

a 2.5% solution of KOH, and then a solution of iodine or KJ.

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